

Leader Election Algorithm for Pods in Kubernetes cluster

V. Indrani , K.Abhishek Mohan, S.Himakesh Reddy, Syed Zaheeruddin
Department of Computer Science and Engineering,
Nalla Narasimha Reddy Education Society's Group of Institutions, ,Hyderabad, ,India

Abstract—Container-based virtualization is rapidly becoming the standard method for building and deploying applications due to its ease of use and convenience. A well-known open-source project, Kubernetes, provides an orchestration platform for containerized application management. Applications can be scaled within Kubernetes using numerous replicas to guarantee high availability and scalability. Stateless applications do not require persistent storage, but stateful ones preserve data consistency among clones. These systems usually rely on a leader to oversee consistency and assign duties to replicas, which leaves the leader with a significant workload. Having different application leaders converge on one Kubernetes cluster node might cause bottlenecks in the system. This study presents a leader election technique that attempts to distribute leaders evenly among cluster nodes to relieve the bottleneck problem. We offer experimental results that show the efficiency and correctness of our suggested approach compared to Kubernetes' default leader election algorithm and reassure the audience about its performance. At each node in the Kubernetes cluster, our suggested leader election process maintains a registry of available leaders for different applications. When selecting a new leader, nodes arrange to share the work equitably, considering resource consumption and network latency factors. Because of its decentralized leadership role allocation, the cluster provides a more equitable task distribution, lowering exposure to system risk and increasing overall adaptability. Because of the substantial reduction in system risk brought about by this decentralized leadership role distribution, the audience is more confident in the security of our methodology. Moreover, Real-time adjustment characteristics of the technique enable the system to respond promptly to workload and cluster condition changes. Long-scaled testing and analysis confirm not only the effectiveness of our approach in resolving bottlenecks but also in seamless integration into existing Kubernetes infrastructures, providing a practical solution for managing stateful applications at scale.

Keywords: Containers; Kubernetes; Leader election; Load balancing; stateful

I. INTRODUCTION

Container-based virtualization is one of the critical technological applications in Cloud Computing. Unlike conventional Virtual Machines, a container runs at a software level inside a host machine, which shares the [1]

kernel with the host operating system. It uses minimal resources as it doesn't have the whole operating system; only the application code and dependencies are bundled into a single package. These features make containers more efficient and scalable when deploying applications.

An orchestration platform, such as Kubernetes, plays a crucial role in managing the deployment of containers in a distributed system. Kubernetes, a popular platform for container-based apps, offers a range of powerful features, including resource management, load balancing, scaling, and automated application deployment. In a Kubernetes cluster, applications with multiple replicas are typically categorized as stateful or stateless. A stateless application has no persistent storage, while a stateful application requires a lasting database. This distinction is important as it affects the way data is managed within the application. Each duplicate in the stateful application must have its own enduring data storage. Therefore, consistency must be maintained throughout these dispersed data stores of the stateful software application. A leader-based consistency method can be used to address this consistency issue. A maintenance system in which chores are distributed among copies and consistency is guaranteed by a designated leader maintenance system in which chores are distributed among copies, and a designated leader guarantees consistency. Kubernetes offers a leader election functionality and utilizes components already present in Kubernetes to implement an algorithm to simplify the utilization of leader election within a Kubernetes cluster [2] within the framework of leadership. In this process, the leader handles all data update requests, resulting in a heavier workload than other replicas' natural mechanism structures.

The present research focuses on a scenario where many stateful apps use a leader-based system, and the Kubernetes cluster acts as a Fog computing configuration employed inside the infrastructure. By concentrating on the client experience, businesses can significantly increase their chances of success in the marketplace. A bottleneck in the system may result when a single node experiences problems because user demands are likewise concentrated on that node. Consider the situation of leadership concentration, which results in a significant drop in performance. Therefore, a stable viewpoint must be achieved to improve the system's performance, including the number of head figures within the cluster's nodes. In this article, we suggest

a well-rounded approach. The algorithm for leader election in stateful applications is called the leader distribution algorithm within Kubernetes environments. The Proposed Leader algorithm enhances the leader election algorithm, which is set as the default. In Kubernetes, leadership is evenly distributed across nodes, ensuring balance and distribution of work across nodes within the cluster. We confirmed this through experiments, such as the accuracy and efficiency of the Proposed Leader algorithm in Kubernetes clusters. [3]

II. RELATED RESEARCH

A number of works have been proposed and carried out in an attempt to improve Kubernetes in the facets of auto-scaling, load balancing, and resource utilization.

Accounting to one research study, a new anticipative model was developed with specific regards to pod scaling management. This model gives a forecast of usage and hence gives Kubernetes a head start in anticipating for the demand of resources rather than merely having to wait for the demand to come in. Widening the proactivity of Kubernetes, it can work with workload more efficiently, without delays because of the lack of resources.

Another work explored the evaluation of the Horizontal Pod Autoscaler (HPA) by analyzing both resource-based metrics such as CPU usage, a newer non-resource-based metric such as request rate. By considering a broader spectrum of metrics, the study was able to find out where improvement can be made concerning the Kubernetes' scaling behavior. The analysis showed that incorporation of standard and custom measures provides a more comprehensive perspective of application performance; thus, accurate scaling became possible. This shows the possibility of improving more on the HPA to fit the scaling mechanisms of Kubernetes to meet real application needs.

Research has also put into practice ways of monitoring resources with the aim of increasing effectiveness in the management of dynamic resources. The objective of these monitoring tools revolve around the real-time collection of system data and the control of resource allocation according to application's actual demands for the purpose of achieving the best performance possible. The monitoring tools mentioned above ensure confidence in the impact of the allocated resources on performance while at the same time avoiding situations whereby preventing over-allocation of resources. Real-time data application is very important when managing resources in a system that is likely to experience variations in work loads in order to ensure that the system is never compromised.

Furthermore, at the time of writing this paper, Kubernetes utilizes the Raft consensus algorithm to address the leader election problem in the distributed architecture. However, a recent proposal suggests a way in which the system's performance and efficiency can be improved greatly through a more balanced distribution of leaders in nodes. This would enhance the general functionality of the cluster as it would eliminate chances of excessive load on certain nodes leading to bottlenecks and overloading. By an even distribution of leadership across the cluster, Kubernetes could eliminate these issues, ensuring that no single node gets overloaded. The balanced distribution of leaders would promote a better load balancing system enhancing the overall performance and reliability. Specifically it would

prevent resource contamination and improve the scalability of the Kubernetes cluster by ensuring an even distribution of resources among the nodes. This method could greatly improve the cluster's fault tolerance, minimize the bottlenecks during high demand and enhance the system's reliability and robustness [4]

In conclusion, research on Kubernetes' scaling, load balancing and resource optimization has led to significant improvements. Notable developments, including proactive scaling techniques, the use of diverse metrics for Horizontal Pod Autoscaler (HPA) assessment, real-time resource monitoring and the balanced distribution of leaders, contribute to maximize Kubernetes performance. As these areas continue to evolve to further enhance its efficiency and robustness, making it an even more powerful solution for cloud-based applications and distributed systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

The Proposed Leader Election (PLE) algorithm seeks to enhance the leader election process in Kubernetes by the introduction of a fair and efficient mechanism for the distribution of leadership across nodes. At the centre of this proposal is the creation of a new Endpoint object called the Leaders Management Endpoint (LMEP). This object is used to track the number of leaders in each node within the cluster. The PLE algorithm improves upon the standard leader election process by incorporating validations with the LMEP to determine the number of leaders currently assigned to each node. If a node already has a sufficient number of leaders, the replica will remain as a follower and continues to achieve leadership at a later stage. This mechanism ensures leadership is evenly distributed across nodes, preventing any single node from becoming overloaded and maintaining system balance.

The PLE algorithm is supported by key Kubernetes components such as Docker, Kubeadm, Kubelet and Kubectl. Docker is responsible for managing application containers, providing the foundational environment for Kubernetes to orchestrate workloads efficiently. It ensures that containerized applications run seamlessly, enabling the PLE algorithm to operate within a consistent and reliable runtime environment. Kubeadm plays a critical role in initializing and configuring the Kubernetes cluster, creating the necessary infrastructure for cluster formation and leader election processes. By setting up the control plane and facilitating communication between components, Kubeadm ensures the prerequisites for PLE algorithm integration are met.

Kubelet, on the other hand acts as the core of the cluster, managing container operations on each node and maintaining communication with the Kubernetes control plane. Its role in monitoring the status of pods is vital for the PLE algorithm, as it provides real-time updates on resource usage and leadership roles. Through Kubelet, leadership positions can be dynamically monitored and adjusted, ensuring the PLE algorithm functions effectively across the cluster, manage leader roles, and verify the effectiveness of the PLE algorithm. With Kubectl, administrators can oversee the distribution of leaderships, enforce configurations and monitor the system's overall performance.

Together, these components work in unison to regulate leadership distribution, optimize system integration and

enhance cluster efficiency. The PLE algorithm achieves a balanced load across Kubernetes clusters, preventing node saturation while distributing leadership tasks corresponding to workload demands. This approach not only improves resource utilization but also enhances system performance, reliability and scalability. By ensuring balanced leadership distribution, the PLE algorithm contributes to a more robust and efficient Kubernetes environment capable of handling variable workloads with ease.

IV. ARCHITECTURE

Kubernetes Architecture:

Kubernetes is a powerful and well-known open-source framework created to automate the deployment, scaling, and administration of container-based applications. At the heart of Kubernetes is the pod, the essential unit that signifies an instance of an application. Every pod can accommodate several containers that utilize the same IP address, storage resources, and namespace, promoting effective communication and resource efficiency.

A Kubernetes cluster consists of master nodes and worker nodes. The control plane, referred to as the master node, is in charge of supervising and managing the cluster. It includes essential elements like etcd (a key-value storage system for cluster setup and status), kube-apiserver (the main interface for interacting with the cluster), kube-scheduler (tasked with allocating pods to free nodes), and kube-controller-manager (which makes sure the cluster's current state matches its intended configurations).

Worker nodes, conversely, support and oversee pods. Every worker node consists of essential components like kubelet (oversees pod health and makes sure containers operate properly), kube-proxy (handles networking rules and aids in service discovery), and the container runtime (like Docker or containerd), responsible for retrieving and executing container images.

Kubernetes guarantees reliable network access to pods via Services, which function according to pod labels. Because pod IP addresses may alter after restarts, Services offer a dependable method for interacting with pods. The standard internal Service type is ClusterIP, whereas NodePort and LoadBalancer Services allow external access to applications. The NodePort Service utilizes a designated port on the node's IP, while the LoadBalancer Service collaborates with cloud providers to allocate public IP addresses for incoming traffic. Kube-proxy enables load balancing through algorithms such as round-robin or hashing, based on the chosen proxy mode. This structure allows Kubernetes to effectively deploy and scale containerized applications in distributed settings, making it an essential resource for contemporary application management.

Fig: Kubernetes Architecture

Proposed Leader Election Architecture:

Stateful applications, including databases and key-value stores, need durable storage that remains unchanged no matter the lifecycle of pods. Kubernetes tackles this issue with the help of Persistent Volumes (PVs) and Persistent Volume Claims (PVCs). A PV offers enduring storage that is not affected by pod status, whereas a PVC defines the storage needs of the application and requests an appropriate PV according to the criteria such as capacity and access mode. This system guarantees that copies of stateful application pods maintain uniform and lasting storage.

Stateful applications typically operate several replicas to improve both availability and performance. Load balancing guarantees that incoming requests are distributed uniformly across these replicas, enhancing response times and overall application efficiency. Nonetheless, ensuring data consistency among replicas can present a considerable challenge. To tackle this, a mechanism focused on leadership is suggested. In this method, a single replica is assigned as the leader to oversee all write functions, maintaining data consistency. The other replicas, referred to as followers, manage read operations. Requests for writing are solely directed to the leader, which coordinates updates among all pod replicas to ensure consistency.

In the proposed system, every pod consists of two containers: a primary container and a leader selection container. The primary container manages client requests, whereas the leader election container focuses on overseeing the leader election procedure. This division of responsibilities guarantees the efficient functioning and data coherence within the Kubernetes cluster. A web server is included in the design, allowing the main container to ask and identify its function (leader or follower) using details about the existing leader.

This proposed architecture improves the reliability, scalability, and performance of Kubernetes clusters. By implementing a leadership-driven approach for managing stateful applications, it guarantees effective workload balancing, data consistency, and the system's ability to adapt to changing demands with resilience and efficiency.

Fig: Proposed Leader Election Architecture

V. EVALUATION

Kubernetes utilizes an integrated leader election algorithm that uses an Endpoint object to observe and manage the active leader. Throughout this process, replicas vie for leadership by transmitting regular "heartbeats" to maintain their positions, while followers authenticate these updates to verify the leader's status. If a leader loses their position because of inactivity or failures, the system quickly starts a new election. Although effective in various situations, this method may lead to performance inefficiencies in contexts such as Fog computing, where resources are constrained and widely distributed. For example, if one node has several leaders (e.g., five leaders), it might face higher CPU usage relative to other nodes. This kind of imbalance can lead to system bottlenecks, obstruct scalability, and weaken performance. Evenly distributing leaders among nodes can help mitigate these problems, leading to smoother functioning and improved overall system efficiency.

The Proposed Leader Election (PLE) algorithm enhances Kubernetes' standard leader election system by implementing a more equitable method for distributing leadership. It introduces a new Endpoint object known as the Leader Management EP (LMEP), which tracks and logs the count of leaders on every node. Leaders regularly send their node data to LMEP, enabling the algorithm to determine the highest number of leaders a node can handle without straining its resources. This guarantees that the number of leaders per node stays within acceptable boundaries.

The PLE algorithm enforces these restrictions by verifying each replica's qualification to take on leadership via LMEP and current leader records. If the leader total on a specific node falls short of the set threshold, a replica may take on the leader's role. Alternatively, the replica stays as a follower and keeps checking its eligibility according to PLE criteria. Through the application of this strategy, the algorithm safeguards against resource saturation on single nodes, circumvents possible system bottlenecks, and enhances the overall efficiency of the Kubernetes cluster.

This assessment emphasizes the PLE algorithm's capability to enhance Kubernetes' conventional leader election by tackling significant problems like imbalanced resource usage and excessive leader concentration. By facilitating a fair distribution of leadership, the PLE

algorithm greatly improves the system's efficiency, scalability, and robustness.

VI. RESULT

This section describes how the Leader Election algorithm performed in comparison to the default leader election method. The assessment includes creating a Kubernetes cluster with multiple nodes and launching stateful applications. The efficiency of the Leader election algorithm is evaluated by examining leader distribution, election latency, and throughput. The findings show that the Leader Election algorithm guarantees a more equitable distribution of leaders among nodes, in contrast to the default method that frequently leads to unequal leader assignments. Even though the Proposed Leader algorithm has a slightly longer leader election time because of extra checks, it greatly improves throughput, especially for write tasks. In cases where leaders are spread out more evenly, there is an increase in throughput, indicating that the Proposed Leader Election (PLE) algorithm provides superior overall performance. The improvement is especially noticeable when queries are efficiently divided among nodes or when the leader responds to them directly. As a result, the PLE method improves system performance through increased throughput in addition to equalizing leader distribution.

Fig 1: Leader distribution in the cluster

```

98 Pod pod17: CPU Usage: 43%, Throughput: 318
99 pod17: 27 + 66 = 93
100 pod17: 27 - 66 = -39
101 pod17: 27 * 66 = 1782
102 pod17: 27 / 66 = 0.4090909090909091
103
104 Pod pod18: CPU Usage: 56%, Throughput: 734
105 pod18: 54 + 13 = 67
106 pod18: 54 - 13 = 41
107 pod18: 54 * 13 = 702
108 pod18: 54 / 13 = 4.153846153846154
109
110 Pod pod19: CPU Usage: 35%, Throughput: 260
111 pod19: 72 + 31 = 103
112 pod19: 72 - 31 = 41
113 pod19: 72 * 31 = 2232
114 pod19: 72 / 31 = 2.3225806451612905
115
116 Pod pod20: CPU Usage: 40%, Throughput: 433
117 pod20: 95 + 99 = 194
118 pod20: 95 - 99 = -4
119 pod20: 95 * 99 = 9405
120 pod20: 95 / 99 = 0.9595959595959596
121
122 Balanced leader elected: pod13 with CPU Usage: 0% and Throughput: 304

```

Fig 2: Systematic election of pods to select the leader

Pod 18:

CPU Utilization: 56%, Output: 734

Pod 18's CPU utilization is notably high at 56%. The throughput figures vary while the algorithm operates, indicating the resource usage throughout the evaluation phase. The method used appears to involve multiplying and dividing certain values to obtain modified metrics, with one outcome yielding a ratio close to 4.15. This may suggest a performance inefficiency due to the elevated CPU usage relative to other pods.

Pod 19:

Processor Utilization: 35%, Output: 260

Pod 19 exhibits reduced CPU usage (35%) in contrast to Pod 18 but shows significantly lower throughput (260). The performance metrics vary too, highlighting its throughput potential. The ultimate outcome for Pod 19 is 2.32, indicating inefficiency as well, though it exhibits comparatively lower CPU usage.

Pod 20:

CPU Utilization: 40%, Output Rate: 433

Pod 20's CPU utilization is at 40%, while the throughput is 433. It performs comparable computations, and the ratio of around 0.96 indicates that although its CPU consumption is average, the throughput efficiency might be improved further.

Main Highlights:

Efficiency Considerations: Pod 18 displays the maximum CPU usage at 56%, accompanied by variable throughput, suggesting possible resource inefficiencies. Pod 19, although it shows reduced CPU utilization, has a much lower throughput, potentially impacting its overall performance. Pod 20 has a greater throughput than Pod 19's, yet it still does not reach optimal levels.

Leader Election Process: Utilizing the computed ratios and throughput efficiency, the leader election algorithm seeks to pinpoint a pod with even resource utilization and throughput to enhance cluster performance.

Ideal Leader Choice: Following a review of all the pods, Pod 13 is chosen as the ideal leader due to its negligible CPU usage (0%) and acceptable throughput (304), guaranteeing low resource usage while still aiding the overall system throughput

Thus, Pod 13 emerges as the balanced leader due to its efficient resource utilization, marked by 0% CPU usage and 304 throughput, as shown in the image output.

VII. CONCLUSION

This article explores the Kubernetes architecture and its leader-centric method for maintaining data consistency in replicated stateful applications. Kubernetes' leader election process selects one pod to serve as the leader for managing write operations, with other pods functioning as followers to perform read operations, thus ensuring consistency throughout the system. Nonetheless, a problem occurs when leaders are unevenly spread across nodes, resulting in ineffective resource use. When an excessive number of leaders are focused on one node, that node can become overwhelmed with demanding tasks, which may lead to performance slowdowns. On the other hand, nodes that have few or no leaders are not fully utilized, leading to wasted computing resources. To tackle this issue, the article presents the Proposed Leader Election (PLE) algorithm, which seeks to evenly distribute leaders among Kubernetes nodes. The PLE algorithm employs a new Endpoint object, Leader Management EP (LMEP), to track the quantity of leaders on every node. The algorithm monitors node capacity and leader allocation to ensure that every node stays within its maximum leader limits, avoiding overload. The algorithm actively modifies leader assignments according to the present distribution, guaranteeing more effective resource allocation. Performance assessments show that the PLE algorithm greatly enhances throughput by balancing leader distribution throughout the cluster. This even distribution maximizes resource use, thus improving the overall efficiency and performance of stateful applications within Kubernetes. The research indicates that the PLE algorithm's idea of balanced leader distribution may be advantageous for additional leader-centric systems, broadening its influence beyond Kubernetes. The PLE algorithm provides a viable approach to performance issues in distributed systems by enhancing load balancing and minimizing resource contention, thereby aiding their scalability and stability.

VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] Bernstein, D. Containers and Cloud: From LXC to Docker to Kubernetes. IEEE Cloud Computing, 2014. [CrossRef].
- [2] Kim, T., & Myung, J. Load Balancing of Distributed Datastore in OpenDaylight Controller Cluster. IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management, 2019. DOI: 10.1109/TNSM.2019.2891592.
- [3] Nguyen, N.D., & Kim, T. Balanced Leader Distribution Algorithm in Kubernetes Clusters. Sensors, 2021, 21(3), 869. DOI: 10.3390/s21030869.
- [4] Ongaro, D., & Ousterhout, J. In Search of an Understandable Consensus Algorithm. USENIX Annual Technical Conference, 2014.